

Desenvolvimento regional e territorialidades

REGIONAL TYPOLOGY OF COUNTRIES OF THE ORGANIZATION FOR ECONOMIC COOPERATION AND DEVELOPMENT (OECD)

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1 INTRODUÇÃO

OECD 37 Member countries and 5 key partners represent about 80% of world trade and investment. The European Union has a permanent delegation to the OECD. Six Prospective Members have requested OECD membership: Argentina, Brazil, Bulgaria, Croatia, Peru, Romania. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in October 2022 recognized Ukraine as a potential member of its organization and is conducting negotiations on Ukraine's entry into the "club of successful countries". In order to find the best models of regional typology of countries, it is advisable to take into account the experience of foreign countries and develop their own set of instruments in the field of state regulation in accordance with the defined goals and priorities.

2 REFERENCIAL TEÓRICO

The OECD Regional Database collects and publishes statistical indicators at two different geographical levels, namely large regions (Territorial Level 2, TL2) and small regions (Territorial Level 3, TL3). Both levels encompass entire national territories. With some exceptions, TL2 regions represent the first administrative tier of subnational government (i.e. States in the United States, Provinces in Canada, or Régions in France). TL3 regions are smaller territorial units that make-up each TL2 region.

2.1. Methodology to classify regions into predominantly urban, intermediate or predominantly rural, 2011.

Regions of OECD member countries have been classified into Predominantly Urban, Intermediate and Predominantly Rural to take into account geographical differences among them. Comparing the socioeconomic performance of regions of the same type (whether urban or rural) across countries is useful in detecting similar characteristics and development paths.

This typology, based essentially on the percentage of regional population living in urban or rural communities, has proved to be meaningful to better explain regional differences

in economic and labour market performance. However this typology does not take into account the presence of economic agglomerations if they happen to be in neighbouring regions.

The OECD regional typology is applied only to regions at **Territorial Level 3 (TL3)** and it is based on criteria of population density and size of the urban centres located within a region.

The methodology is made of three main steps:

1. The first step of the methodology consists in classifying “local units” (administrative entities at a geographical level lower than TL3) as rural if their population density is below 150 inhabitants per square kilometers [1].

Table 1. Local units of OECD countries Country [2]

Country / Local units	Country / Local units
Australia / Statistical Local Areas (SLA) - ABS	Japan / Municipalities (as of 1999)
Austria / Gemeinden (LAU2)	Korea / Counties
Belgium / Gemeenten/Communes (LAU2)	Luxembourg / Communes (LAU2)
Canada / Census Consolidated Subdivision – Statistics / Canada	Mexico / Municipios
Czech Republic / Obce (LAU2)	Netherlands / Gemeenten (LAU2)
Denmark / Municipalities (before reform)	New Zealand Area Units (Stat. New Zealand)
Finland / Kunnat/Kommuner (LAU2)	Norway / Municipalities
France / Communes (LAU2)	Poland / Gminy (LAU2)
Germany / Verbandsgemeinden	Portugal / Freguesias (LAU2)
Greece / Dimoi/Koinotites (LAU1)	Slovak / Republic Obce (LAU2)
Hungary / Települések (LAU2)	Spain / Municipios (LAU2)
Iceland / Municipalities	Sweden / Kommuner (LAU2)
Ireland / Electoral Districts (LAU2)	Switzerland / Municipalities
Italy / Comuni (LAU2)	Turkey / Districts
	United Kingdom / Wards (or parts thereof) (LAU2)
	United States / Counties

2. The second step consists in aggregating this lower level (local units) into TL3 regions and classifying the latter as “predominantly urban”, “intermediate” and “predominantly rural” using the percentage of population living in rural local units (local units with a population density below 150 inhabitants per square kilometers). TL3 regions are then classified as:

- **Predominantly Urban (PU)**, if the share of population living in rural local units is below 15%;
- **Intermediate (IN)**, if the share of population living in rural local units is between 15% and 50%;

- **Predominantly Rural (PR)**, if the share of population living in rural local units is higher than 50%

Finally, a third step takes into account the size of the urban centres contained in the TL3 regions, and adjusts the classification based on the following rules:

- A region classified as predominantly rural by steps 1 and 2 becomes intermediate if it contains an urban centre of more than 200 000 inhabitants representing at least 25% of the regional population.

- A region classified as intermediate by steps 1 and 2 becomes predominantly urban if it contains an urban centre of more than 500 000 inhabitants representing at least 25% of the regional population.

3 PROCEDIMENTOS METODOLÓGICOS

This article concerns bibliographic research in the context of production of knowledge, as a methodological procedure that offers the researcher the possibility of seeking solutions to a research problem. It recognizes the need to present the scientific method chosen by the researcher; to present the forms of construction of the methodological design and the choice of procedures; and demonstrates how the presentation and analysis of the data obtained is configured.

4 RESULTADOS E DISCUSSÕES

4.1. OECD Extended Regional Typology: The Economic Performance of Remote Rural Regions.

The extended typology is used to compare the dynamics of population and labour markets. Remote rural regions show a stronger decline in population and a faster ageing process than rural regions close to a city. The remoteness of rural regions is in fact a significant factor explaining regional outflows of working age population, confirming that this extended typology captures the economic distance from market and services.

The extended typology only further classifies intermediate and rural regions into remote or close to a populated centre. The resulting classification consists of five types of regions: Predominantly Urban (PU), Intermediate Close to a city (INC), Intermediate Remote (INR), Predominantly Rural Close to a city (PRC) and Predominantly Rural Remote (PRR).

Figure 1.
Extended
Typology Europe

Figure 2.
Extended
Typology North-
America [3]

Table 2. Percentage of the population by extended typology [3]

Country	PU	INC	INR	PRC	PRR	Total
Austria	23%	31%	0%	35%	11%	100%
Belgium	83%	14%	0%	2%	0%	100%
Canada	48%	19%	0%	20%	13%	100%
Czech Republic	11%	84%	0%	5%	0%	100%
Denmark	29%	28%	0%	24%	19%	100%
Finland	26%	9%	4%	42%	20%	100%
France	35%	48%	0%	13%	4%	100%
Germany	56%	26%	0%	18%	0%	100%
Greece	36%	24%	0%	5%	35%	100%
Hungary	17%	42%	0%	22%	19%	100%
Iceland
Ireland	28%	0%	0%	45%	27%	100%
Italy	52%	36%	3%	6%	3%	100%
Mexico	47%	17%	0%	26%	9%	100%
Netherlands	85%	15%	0%	0%	0%	100%
Norway	12%	35%	5%	4%	45%	100%
Poland	23%	29%	2%	45%	1%	100%
Portugal	52%	24%	2%	6%	15%	100%
Slovak Republic	11%	63%	0%	25%	0%	100%
Spain	48%	36%	2%	8%	6%	100%
Sweden	21%	30%	0%	29%	20%	100%
Switzerland	41%	45%	4%	3%	6%	100%
Turkey	47%	25%	0%	22%	5%	100%
United Kingdom	70%	27%	1%	2%	0%	100%
United States	43%	20%	0%	33%	4%	100%

Figure 3. Service areas for 30-min, 60-min and 90-min time frames, North America [3]

4.2. New classification of TL3 Regions based on FUA boundaries, 2019

FUAs consist of densely populated cities and of adjacent local units with high levels of commuting (travel-to-work flows) towards the densely populated cities.

The methodology to delineate FUAs consists of three main steps:

1. Identification of cities: Population grid data at 1 km² are used to define urban centres. The “city” or “core” is made up of contiguous units that have more than 50% of their populations living within an urban centre.
2. Identification of interconnected cities that are part of the same functional urban area: Two cities are considered as being part of the same FUA if more than 15% of the population of any of the two cities commutes to work to the other city.
3. Definition of the commuting zones surrounding cities: The commuting zone of the FUA groups the surrounding local units that are linked to cities by the commuting pattern of their workforce.

The method presented in this paper classifies TL3 regions into metropolitan and nonmetropolitan according to the following criteria:

- Metropolitan TL3 region (MR), if more than 50% of its population lives in a FUA of at least 250 thousand inhabitants. MRs are further classified according to their level of access to FUAs of different sizes into:
 - Large metro TL3 region (MR-L), if more than 50% of its population lives in a FUA of at least 1.5 million inhabitants.

- Metro TL3 region (MR-M), if the TL3 region is not a large metro region and 50% of its population lives in a FUA of at least 250 thousand inhabitants.

Figure 4. Drive-time polygon (isochrone) for the FUA of Oostende, Belgium [4]

- **Non-metropolitan TL3 region (NMR)**, if less than 50% of its population lives in a FUA. NMRs are further classified according to their level of access to FUAs of different sizes into:

- **With access to a metro TL3 region (NMR-M)**, if more than 50% of its population lives within a 60 minute drive from a metro (a FUA with more than 250 thousand people); or if the TL3 region contains more than 80% of the area of a FUA of at least 250 thousand inhabitants.

- **With access to a small/medium city TL3 region (NMR-S)**, if the TL3 region does not have access to a metro and 50% of its population has access to a small or medium city (a FUA of more than 50 thousand and less than 250 thousand inhabitants) within a 60 minute drive; or if the TL3 region contains more than 80% of the area of a small or medium city.

Remote TL3 region (NMR-R), if the TL3 region is not classified as NMR-M or NMR-S, i.e. if 50% of its population does not have access to any FUA within a 60 minute drive.

Figure 5. Categorization of TL3 regions: North America and Chile

Figure 6. Categorization of TL3 regions: Europe. Metro areas > 250 000 inhabitants; 60-minute drive time [4]

Figure 7. Categorization of TL3 regions-Asia and Oceania. Metro areas > 250 000 inhabitants; 60-minute drive time [4]

5 CONSIDERAÇÕES FINAIS

Developing a statistically robust and internationally comparable system of classification of territorial units has been a topic that can represent a valuable tool to analyse socio-economic trends across different types of regions in a consistent way across countries. This would allow assessing, among many other things, how trends in GDP per capita, population, employment or productivity are different in countries between different types of regions.

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